

Empowering Afro-Colombian Women on Data Science in Public Health: Workshop Report

Quibdó, Universidad Tecnológica Del Chocó

July 26 -28, 2023

Workshop report

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Table of Contents

Workshop Overview.....	4
Agenda.....	4
Initial characterization.....	9
Motivation and expectations.....	13
Development and evaluation of activities.....	17
Evaluation of the course-workshop.....	23
sivirep test.....	28
Conclusions and recommendations.....	34
Acknowledgement.....	36

Workshop Overview

Location: Quibdó, Universidad Tecnológica Del Chocó

Date: July 26th, 27th and 28th, 2023

Motivation

The response to epidemic emergencies and their impact on public health currently requires rapid analysis of large amounts of data for monitoring, management and decision making in public health. Likewise, the use of tools and their compatibility with different information systems is increasingly required. The R programming language, being an open, free, and open-source environment, has become a flexible tool with advanced functionalities. It enables epidemiology and public health professionals to better manipulate and analyze data, facilitating more informed and timely public health responses.

Objective

To develop skills in using R for the analysis and visualization of epidemiological data to support decision-making in public health.

Target population

Professionals of the Chocó Departmental Secretary of Health and Municipal Health Secretariat of Quibdó, students of the Faculty of Health in their last semesters, teachers of the Faculty of Health of the Technological University of Chocó and other health workers keen on acquiring basic R programming skills for epidemiological data analysis.

Agenda

Day 1- Wednesday, July 26, 2023

Activity	Objective	Description
<p style="text-align: center;">Characterization workshop</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Time: 1 hour</p>	<p>To explore participants' expectations, experiences and challenges in working with data in public health.</p>	<p>As an icebreaker activity, a web/spider web was made in which each participant introduced him/herself and completed the sentence "From my experience, working with health data is...". Then, in groups, each participant should place themselves in the places of the data cycle according to their work. There, they reflected on the challenges involved in working with data in their work and the expectations of how this course-workshop could help solve these identified problems or challenges.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Conference: "Data Science for the control of epidemics epidemics and its impact on public health".</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Time: 1 hour</p>	<p>To motivate participants in the topics to be addressed during the course and to provide an overview of the importance and understanding of how data science has become an essential tool in the management of epidemics and its role in public health decision making.</p>	<p>The talk provided a perspective on data management and analysis in public health, especially in the epidemiology of infectious diseases. Starting from a historical perspective, mentioning figures who have made contributions to both data science and public health, such as Florence Nightingale. Next, some challenges and opportunities for data analysis in public health are discussed, followed by the presentation of the Epiverse TRACE-LAC project and the development of software for data science in public health for decision-making.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Workshop "Practical introduction of R and RStudio"</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Time: 1.5 hours</p>	<p>To recognize R and RStudio; their structures and the process of importing, exporting and transforming databases with Tidyverse.</p>	<p>This workshop introduced the different elements in the RStudio interface, data structures in R, and data handling with Tidyverse.</p>

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Activity	Objective	Description
<p>Epidemiological data cleaning and organization workshop</p> <p>Time: 2 hours</p>	<p>To explore participants' expectations, experiences and challenges in working with data in public health.</p>	<p>This workshop was expected to address the cleaning and organization of epidemiological data using RStudio.</p>
<p>Workshop "Practical introduction to the principles of visualisation of data in ggplot"</p> <p>Time: 1 hour</p>	<p>Recognize the functions that make up the ggplot2 package and make basic graphs with the ggplot2 structure.</p>	<p>This workshop focused on the use of the ggplot2 package, which is the R package that allows visualization.</p>

Day 2- Thursday, July 27, 2023

Activity	Objetive	Description
<p>Workshop on risk communication</p> <p>Time: 1 hour</p>	<p>Recognize key elements and strategies of public health risk communication.</p>	<p>This session began with a brief talk on elements and examples of risk communication strategies in public health. Then, through a ladder board game, participants in groups completed challenges, answered questions, and discussed concepts and strategies for effectively and accurately communicating information related to public health risks. The aim was to inform, educate, and empower populations and communities in the face of emergencies or disease outbreaks.</p>

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Activity	Objetivo	Description
<p>Workshop "Introduction to RMarkdown"</p> <p>Time: 1 hour</p>	<p>Recognizing the importance of creating reports in Rmarkdown and learning to use Rmarkdown basics.</p>	<p>This workshop covered the basic use of the RMarkdown format that allows, thanks to its integration with the code, the presentation of reports with updated data, tables and graphs without the need to import graphs or manually create tables.</p>
<p>Introduction to sivirep workshop - Basic reporting workshop with sivirep</p> <p>Time: 2 hours</p>	<p>To introduce the Sivirep package and identify its key functionalities for generating basic reports.</p>	<p>This workshop involved a presentation and user testing of the Sivirep package, demonstrating its utilization for creating basic epidemiological reports.</p>
<p>Group workshop on regional report sivirep</p> <p>Time: 3 hours</p>	<p>Utilize the Sivirep package for the analysis of one of the diseases with the greatest impact in the region as a tool for analysis and decision-making in each event.</p>	<p>In this workshop, four groups were formed, and each was assigned one of the following diseases to analyze in the Chocó region: Dengue, Malaria, Maternal Mortality, and Suicide Attempt. In addition to generating the basic report, each group had to adjust the report and add new functionalities to analyze the behavior of each event and the possible scenarios for decision-making. This report and analysis were to be presented in the next session to an audience chosen from, for example, the general public, decision-makers, students, among others.</p>

Day 3- Friday, July 28, 2023

Activity	Objetivo	Descripción
<p>Socialization of reports, findings and decision making by groups.</p> <p>Time: 3 hours</p>	<p>Present and socialize the regional reports made with <i>sivirep</i> for the analysis and decision making of each event.</p>	<p>Each group presented in 10 minutes to the rest the findings and possible recommendations or decision making of the event studied based on the data analysis and visualization provided by the report made through the <i>sivirep</i> package. Then 5 minutes were given for questions from the rest of the participants and feedback from those who developed <i>sivirep</i> and the representative of the National Institute of Health (INS), among other team members.</p>
<p>Panel "Data analysis for monitoring, management and decision making in public health."</p> <p>Time: 1.5 hours</p>	<p>Discuss possibilities and experiences in data analysis for monitoring, management and decision making in public health.</p>	<p>This panel was expected to include the participation of two of the leading participants in surveillance in the region, as well as members of the team and the representative of the National Institute of Health (INS).</p>

Initial characterization

The participant group was mainly composed of faculty members from the Health Faculty of the Technological University of Chocó, support professionals, coordinators, and surveillance focal points from the Municipal Health Secretariat and the Departmental Health Secretariat of Chocó. Additionally, participants from the ASOREDIPARCHOCO Association of Midwives in Chocó were involved. In total, 20 people registered, of which 17 people completed the course-workshop (85%).

Chart 1. Profile distribution

Although most participants study or work in a health-related area, the disciplinary background (undergraduate) of those who attended the workshops is diverse (see Chart 2), with health sciences -and nursing, in particular- being the majority disciplinary field of study.

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Chart 2. Disciplinary Background

Out of the total participants, 85% identify as female.

Chart 3. Gender Distribution

As for age distribution, the majority falls between 32 and 45 years old.

Chart 4. Age distribution

Regarding data management and tools for analysis, out of the total registered individuals, only one-third had used R and RStudio at some point. Several participants expressed that they had previous experiences learning R that were not satisfactory for many; "this is the third time I try to learn R. If it wasn't this time, then it's over," one participant stated.

Chart 5. Use of R

The majority of participants work with data related to maternal-child health and infectious diseases. Although some individuals mentioned not currently working

with quantitative data, they expressed interest in learning about data analysis in public health. This is noteworthy, especially for some professionals from ASOREDIPARCHOCO, who expressed their interest in learning data work methods to enhance their data collection efforts.

Regarding computational skills, the majority of participants mentioned Excel - "blessed Excel," as one of them would say - as the frequently used tool for data management in their organizations and research. Only four people reported having knowledge in data management tools other than Excel, such as SPSS, Stata, Graphpad, Image J, Python, and C++ (knowledge of the latter was reported by one of the men from the engineering field).

Motivation and expectations

In order to understand the reasons why participants decided to attend the course-workshop, a questionnaire was conducted beforehand to inquire about their motivation for attending this space. According to this information, it was found that for the majority of participants, the main motivation was to learn R programming and apply it to their work in teaching and public health.

"To acquire and update knowledge that will allow me to make use of the tools and generate rapid responses to possible outbreaks or epidemics."

Some individuals were already familiar with R and had even made attempts to learn its use, but due primarily to physical resource constraints such as computer availability, they were unable to successfully complete their training in using this tool. On the other hand, for the majority, the use of R is highly relevant and presents an opportunity to support their work tasks.

A distinguishing factor in this group of participants was the motivation to learn how to use the tool for the benefit of the community.

"Enhance my research skills, and then utilize them for the benefit of others."

"To be able to share that knowledge with the communities where I work after learning."

On the other hand, regarding expectations and what participants hoped to learn in this space, it was evident that while most participants sought to learn the tool to use it in their work, the importance of research training was also highlighted.

"Properly learning the tool thoroughly and apply it to my duties as a surveillance referent, for studies, research, and teaching."

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On the other hand, while it was clear to most from the beginning and the call for participation about the use of R in the training, some expected it to focus more on statistical analysis (descriptive, inferential, and multivariate) rather than model management.

Finally, part of the results from the opening exercise of the course-workshop, prior to the start of the activities focused on R and RStudio, allowed us to understand, through the construction of a network/web, the problems, challenges, experiences, and emotions associated with working with health data.

In addition to confirming their interest in learning tools that allow for better management and analysis of data in their work, some participants made mention of metaphors related to bodies of water such as rain and the sea, which hold great significance in a region like Chocó. This region is crossed by the Atrato River, with permanent rainfall (300 out of 365 days a year), and is also the only department in Colombia with coastlines on both the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans.

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illustration "Un mar de emociones" by Maria Paula Forero.

For the female participants, discussing working with data placed them in "a sea of emotions" that, like the waves of the sea, involves a back and forth between the frustration and gratification of, on one hand, a routine and exhausting job that requires "PATIENCE (in capital letters)," and on the other hand, a job that has an impact and results on people's lives once decisions are made.

On another note, the use of data that remains at the local level due to lack of analytical capabilities and infrastructure problems emerged as a constant concern expressed in this sea of emotions. The sea also alludes to an overwhelming universe of data that gets lost without further analysis or use by those who could do so, and here another metaphor emerges to address this issue, which is that of rain. "Who hasn't been caught in the rain?" remarked one of the participants to

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speak of the shared experience of feeling the data like drops that, without the proper tool, end up on the ground without containment. Drops and data, when out of place, are perceived as chaotic.

"Channeling to a point" accompanies the rain metaphor to talk about the action of organizing, analyzing, visualizing, and effectively communicating a flow of information. This represents the main demand of the participants, as their primary motivation can be summarized in this need to have tools to channel (organize and utilize) data and have a greater impact.

Development and evaluation of activities

Day 1- Wednesday, July 26, 2023

Name of Activity	Comments	Results
<p>Characterization Workshop</p> <p>Time: 2 hours</p>	<p>Participation was active and the exercise allowed validating the relevance of the following activities and expanding the Risk Communication activity.</p> <p>On the other hand, for the development of the Training Kit, this workshop allowed us to validate the need for available training materials in different geographical locations and the interest in data science training.</p>	<p>A series of definitions and experiences regarding working with data were obtained from the participants. Additionally, a list of problems and challenges related to working with data in public health in the region was compiled. Finally, the expectations for the course-workshop were acknowledged.</p>
<p>Conference: "Data science for epidemic control and its impact on public health".</p> <p>Time: 1 hour</p>	<p>This talk allowed for a deeper discussion about the Epiverse TRACE-LAC project and the packages being developed in the development component.</p> <p>For the training kit, it is essential to include historical milestones in topics related to data science and epidemiology of infectious diseases. Additionally, it is important to provide historical references that participants can identify with.</p>	<p>The talk sparked astonishment regarding the contributions of figures like Florence Nightingale, who is known for her contributions to nursing but less known for her work in data visualization. Furthermore, the talk motivated interest in learning more about the work being done within the Epiverse TRACE-LAC project.</p>

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Name of Activity	Comments	Results
<p>Practical introduction to R and RStudio</p> <p>Time: 3 hours</p>	<p>Esta actividad estaba programada para 1 hora y media y tomó al menos el doble del tiempo dada la heterogeneidad del grupo, los recursos físicos, el manejo del idioma inglés y el nivel de habilidades digitales de algunas de las participantes.</p> <p>Para el kit de entrenamiento, es importante explicar cuatro estructuras básicas: lista, vector, matriz y tabla de datos. Además se deben incluir los ejemplos y prácticas dentro de los tutoriales de video.</p> <p>La forma en que Zulma explica y va evaluando los conceptos es clave para replicarlo en otros talleres y actividades. Finalmente, nombrar las palabras en inglés cómo se leen en español resulta ser útil para agilizar la actividad en términos de ubicar más fácil las funcionalidades.</p>	<p>Each participant was able to identify the different elements of the RStudio interface, some of its structures, and project management. Additionally, they imported data and learned how to use Tidyverse.</p> <p>Finally, they were able to recognize the fundamentals, basic elements, and structures, which was crucial for understanding the language and subsequent handling of it. This exercise was marked as a differentiating factor from previous experiences with learning R.</p>
<p>Epidemiological data cleaning and organization workshop</p> <p>Time: NA</p>	<p>Due to time constraints, it was not possible to complete it. Its structure was too long for the estimated time.</p> <p>For the training kit, it's important to review the workshop's structure and, if possible, divide it into multiple parts.</p>	

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Name of Activity	Comments	Results
<p>Practical introduction to the principles of data visualization in ggplot</p> <p>Time: 1.5 hours</p>	<p>The number of exercises was reduced due to time constraints and the amount of information covered during the session.</p> <p>For the training kit, the video tutorial with examples will allow for a step-by-step guide similar to what was provided during the in-person workshop.</p>	<p>Each participant was able to create a series of basic plots using the ggplot2 library.</p>

Day 2- Thursday, July 27, 2023

Name of Activity	Comments	Results
<p>Risk Communication Workshop</p> <p>Time: 1.5 hours</p>	<p>The workshop requires at least an hour and a half for its development and discussion. The gamification strategy was motivating for the participants.</p> <p>For the training kit, the importance of a unit on this topic is validated, and it is also proposed that the game be replicable with the community. It is important to review the use of some concepts for the development of the content of this unit.</p>	<p>This was one of the workshops that had a significant impact in terms of methodology, topic, and resources used. The participants were enthusiastic, active, and receptive to the proposed activity. They also expressed the importance of the methodology for replication in their work groups and communities.</p>

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Name of Activity	Comments	Results
<p>Practical introduction to RMarkdown</p> <p>Time: 1.5 hours</p>	<p>The importance of this workshop is reflected in the subsequent exercise on the sivirep challenge, in which participants will need to use this tool. Therefore, it's important that this workshop takes place just before the explanation of sivirep.</p> <p>For the training kit, it is recommended to create a short video tutorial covering the recognition of the RMarkdown interface and its key elements.</p>	<p>Each participant was able to generate a report in PDF or Word format, which allowed them to see the utility of the tool.</p>
<p>Introduction to <i>sivirep</i> - Basic Reporting Workshop with <i>sivirep</i></p> <p>Time: 2 hours</p>	<p>Before starting, an introduction and guided registration to GitHub were conducted. The step-by-step workshop is ideal for time management and achieving the objective.</p> <p>For the training kit, it is suggested to include a short video to provide context about sivirep, followed by a tutorial on generating a basic report similar to the one created during the in-person workshop.</p>	<p>Each participant was able to generate the basic sivirep report and understand the purpose of the package, as well as its scope. From this point on, participants submitted adjustments to the team that could be incorporated into the next version.</p>

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Name of Activity	Comments	Results
<p>Regional report group workshop <i>sivirep</i></p> <p>Time: 3 hours</p>	<p>This workshop requires constant support from the workshop leader and monitors. Conducting the workshop with diseases that have an impact on the region and with which participants work is motivating.</p> <p>For the training kit, it is suggested to create an illustrative video about one of the cases, accompanied by its context. It would be interesting to have one of the participants from the course-workshop participate in this video.</p>	<p>Each group completed their report and a PowerPoint presentation for their presentation and sharing with the rest of the group.</p>

Day 3- Friday, July 28, 2023

Name of Activity	Comments	Results
<p>Socialization of reports, findings and decision making by groups.</p> <p>Time: 3h</p>	<p>Due to the level of participation from the group, this activity took more time than anticipated. However, it was of great importance to hear the participants' experiences and how it connected with what they found in the reports. Additionally, during the presentation, possible improvements for the package were gathered.</p>	<p>Each group successfully presented their report and its findings, along with their experience and the contextualization of these results in the region. They proposed different improvement actions and managed to present according to the audience chosen by each group (students, community, decision-makers, and public health emergency response room).</p>

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Name of Activity	Comments	Results
<p>Panel "Data analysis for monitoring, management and decision making in public health."</p> <p>Time: NA</p>	<p>It was not carried out due to time constraints and because the topics had already been extensively discussed in the previous activity.</p>	

Evaluation of the course-workshop

59% of those who participated responded to the final evaluation survey. For 100% of the participants, the workshops satisfactorily met the proposed objectives, and this course-workshop provided them with useful theoretical and practical learnings for their professional development. Additionally, the content of the workshops was clear, sufficient, and relevant for the participants.

The most notable aspects of the course-workshop were the quality of the lectures and workshops, the topics covered in the talks and workshops, the quality of the facilitators, and the quality of the slides. Regarding time, some participants suggested that it should be extended and even have a second training session. Additionally, there were suggestions for improvements in the quality of physical spaces, particularly concerning internet connectivity.

What did they like most about the course-workshop?

metodología comunicaciones temas maneraequipo
disposición práctica vida profesional
tiempo real La dinámica grupal charla análisis aprendiz
rápido explicación Participación activa
disponibilidad riesgo Calidad tecnica programa R

Among the activities that had the most impact and were memorable were the practices related to R and the sivirep package, as well as the risk communication talk-workshop.

As for the methodology, participants highlighted the explanations, "*the availability of the entire team to assist each learner,*" and empathy.

They also identified active participation and teamwork as important elements of the methodology.

"The sivirep program makes data analysis easy because it provides a quick real-time report."

"The opportunity to optimize work in the territory."

"The detail of the materials, the explanations from the workshop facilitators, and the methodology of the workshops."

What was the most challenging aspect of the course-workshop development for the participants?

Facing the code and programming was the biggest challenge for the participants. Understanding, retaining, and applying commands and the code structure were the

aspects that generated the most difficulties. However, the majority reported having understood the concepts and the general management of the tools.

"It's new for me to work in this program, but I acquired the knowledge."

Suggestions for improving the course-workshop development

In general, those who participated in the different sessions expressed great satisfaction with the design and development of the course-workshop. One suggestion is to extend the duration of the workshops and conduct more than one training session.

"Excellent all around, it exceeded my expectations. It was a very comprehensive course with the opportunity to learn quickly, easily, and in a fun way because my peers encouraged it, and you were accomplices in that unique way of learning in a workshop. Excellent everything, and congratulations. Thank you for sharing your knowledge and company with us. I rate you not only with 5 stars but with double (10) stars, although this survey does not reflect that rating. My respect and admiration to all of you."

Workshop evaluation

The overall rating for the course was 5.0/5.0, and individually, the activities received an average rating of 4.8/5.0.

Name of the activity	Evaluation
Characterization workshop	4.7
Conference "Data Science for epidemic control and its impact on public health".	4.8
Introduction to R and RStudio workshop	4.8
ggplot workshop	4.7
Risk communication workshop	4.8
RMakdown Workshop	4.8
Sivirep Workshop	4.8
Sivirep group workshop	4.8
Socialization of group reports	4.8

Some additional comments on the workshops

Additionally, participants highlighted the methodological aspects of the practices and the human quality of the team that facilitated the different workshops. They also emphasized what they learned in the risk communication workshop and how the practical and guided learning during the course could be adopted in real-life scenarios.

"Very clear explanation, patience and willingness to teach.

practical and useful for daily work. Excellent content and very good tutoring"

On the other hand, since this was a new tool for most participants and it involves handling code, the English language, and digital and computational skills, the process was more challenging for some people to follow. However, they felt motivated and achieved their goal of completing the various exercises and challenges proposed.

It's really interesting, I like it, I'm motivated, but since some of us are beginners, I fall behind and get lost because my learning is slower."

sivirep test

Given that, in addition to the educational process surrounding the use of packages for data analysis in health, the space was designed to conduct a user test with the participants, a final survey was designed to evaluate various aspects of the package. Regarding usability features, there was no doubt that the package is useful and has clear documentation.

Chart 6. Sivirep characteristics evaluations

With the aim of understanding what each user understands about what the package does, when asked "How would you describe sivirep?" and "What does this package do?", the responses converge on it being an R package that uses RMarkdown and Ggplot. Additionally, it was clear that it uses SIVIGILA data and has the cooperation of the National Institute of Health (INS). Finally, they demonstrated an understanding that this package generates reports containing text and graphics for public health data analysis.

Here are some survey responses on how they describe *sivirep*:

"It is a package in cooperation with INS, uses ggplot and RMarkdown, which allows to manipulate and manage data from SIVIGILA to for the delivery of timely and automated reports."

"Useful and fast systematic tool, allowing data synthesis, reporting with text and graphics."

"It allows us to handle data more quickly and make reports more complete."

What did they like most about *sivirep*?

The elements of *sivirep* that generated the most interest and impact were data visualization through graphs, ease of data cleaning, and the speed of report generation.

"sivirep gives you the exact information you need."

What did you like least about *sivirep*?

Given that using *sivirep* requires using R, and for most people it's a new tool, this creates usability challenges that require investing more time in learning and training.

"Personally, you have to practice a lot to master the program."

What was the easiest thing about using *sivirep*?

Some of the advantages reported when using *sivirep* include the reliability of the information, the option to filter data, data cleaning, and report and graph generation. Additionally, it was highlighted that the existing documentation for *sivirep* allowed for successful automated reporting.

"Through the guide it became easy to follow the steps and get the results of the formulas and the report."

What was the most difficult thing about using *sivirep*?

As seen earlier, the coding and programming component is an important factor in the use and adoption of the tool and the package. Therefore, proficiency in R is necessary, and for some people, this creates difficulties in using *sivirep*.

"Having to code or create chunk's for each function or variable I need to analyze."

What would you improve about *sivirep*?

Some improvement suggestions include accessing additional data from SIVIGILA (specifically, having access to the back side of the report form), adjusting the color

scale and time settings, adding the option for municipalities, and providing training materials such as video tutorials.

"At the moment I see the coding extensive, but I believe that practice makes perfect to get the right use out of this package. I would like to see how to do the exercise with the municipalities in the department that I want to work with."

Finally, some suggested improvements for Sivirep are:

- Improve the color scale of the graphs.
- Enhance the visualization of bar graphs.
- Add a time scale, for example, add epidemiological times or periods.
- Include the department and/or municipality names on the map.
- In the grouping and plotting functions, remove the department and municipality fields since the data should be filtered by these parameters beforehand.

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- Including extreme maternal morbidity when importing extreme maternal mortality is important
- Include the calculation rates.
- Include the calculation of incidence.
- Add special populations.
- Adding a trend or scatter plot to show temporalities.
- Including independent rates by sex to avoid bias.
- Creating a map showing the number of cases nationwide vs. cases at the departmental level.
- Adding a function for automatic creation of PowerPoint presentations and infographics from the package.
- Collaborating to make the package an educational tool in epidemiology and analytics in partnership with the INS.
- Add a monitoring module and practice exercises.
- Create a graphical interface (Shiny App or Knit with parameters) that allows selecting variables for analysis.
- Integrate relevant points from the event profile.
- Creating an easy and simple channel to collect user feedback.
- Adding a suggestions section for analyzing the report considering aspects such as:
 - Resource management

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- Health care and education
- Baic sanitation
- Migration crisis
- Armed conflict

Conclusions and recommendations

- The course-workshop achieved its objectives and met the expectations of the participants. The topics that garnered the most attention and had the greatest impact were R and RStudio, Sivirep, and risk communication
- While time is a limiting factor in teaching and learning processes, flexibility in adjusting activities allows us to achieve objectives while considering the needs of participants. Conducting training sessions lasting more than five days (4 hours each) is exhausting for both participants and the team
- It is important to consider characteristics such as group heterogeneity and physical resource capacity when planning the timing and resources for teaching and learning activities.

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- Practical and contextual exercises are essential for maintaining or increasing participants' motivation in the learning process.
- For a group of 20 people, it's important to have at least 2 monitors in addition to the activity leader to accompany the process.
- Conducting a preliminary activity before starting allows participants to get to know each other and also connect with the team.
- Group work facilitates peer teaching dynamics, making the learning process easier.
- Opening up discussion spaces through trigger questions allows for more active participation from participants.
- It's important to create new versions of materials with adjustments made during sessions. This could involve adding examples, removing or modifying content, deleting sections, among other changes.
- The material should be easily accessible using the shortest route possible, such as leaving a shortcut on the desktop of each computer for quicker access to the documentation.
- It is essential to have programs and packages pre-installed in locations with low internet connectivity. Additionally, it is important to have databases, installers, presentations, workshops, etc., stored on removable devices such as USB drives or hard disks.
- Creating tutorial materials such as videos and infographics to support the learning and subsequent use of R, RStudio, and Sivirep is important. These resources will be included in the training kit.
- It's crucial to promote Sivirep as an educational tool for explaining and analyzing events of interest in public health.

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- Conducting user testing for packages like Sivirep allows for a co-creation process, where improvements and adjustments suggested by the end users can make the final product useful and valuable for the community.
- WhatsApp is the most effective means of communication for convening, evaluating, and following up with communities.
- Given the time constraint, it is recommended to send the initial form beforehand and conduct daily evaluations of the activities, in addition to the final evaluation.
- Providing attendance certificates and implementing follow-up strategies along with opportunities for further training are incentives that enhance the experience of training participants.
- For the development of the training kit, the relevance of the topics covered was validated to be included in the course content. Additionally, there should be a review of some concepts and prioritization of topics and exercises for the production of videos that explain the workshops.